

Lead(II) selective sensor based on heterogeneous membranes of chelating inorganic ion exchange resin

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A new inorganic chelating ion exchanger, α -nitroso- β -naphthol sorbed zirconium(IV) tungstophosphate (NN-ZWP) has shown to exhibit significant analytical usefulness for potentiometric sensing towards the lead ions when embedded in a poly(vinyl chloride) matrix membrane. The sensor exhibits a Nernstian response for Pb^{2+} over a wide range of concentration ($1.0 \times 10^{-5} - 5.0 \times 10^{-6} M$) with a response time ~ 40 s and can be used for at least 3 months without any divergence. The proposed membrane sensor reveals good selectivities for Pb^{2+} over a bi- and trivalent metal ions and could be used in a pH range of 5.0–9.0. It has been successfully used for direct determination of Pb^{2+} in soil samples and as an indicator electrode in potentiometric titration of lead ions.

The metal ions can be complexed by a number of different substances, many of ligands have been identified and characterized as for instance the inorganic cations¹ and organic substances as alkaloids². The strong ligands of metal ions, which are present in seawater at very low concentrations³, are not yet completely identified.

Recently, PAN [1-(2-pyridylazo-2-naphthol)] sorbed zinc silicate⁴ and ammonium molybdophosphate⁵, tetracycline hydrochloride sorbed zirconium(IV) tungstophosphate and alumina^{6,7} have been reported for the quantitative separation of metal ions in the literature.

It is well-known understood that the species sorbed on the complexing resins is the free metal ion, only that metal ion present in species totally or partially dissociated in the presence of the resin can be determined. At the same time, the sorption of the metal ion on a resin depends on the stability of the species in the sample, which can be measured by the reaction coefficient of the metal, and on the sorbing properties of the complexing resin⁸. Thus, during the uptake behaviour of metal ions on α -nitroso- β -naphthol sorbed zirconium(IV) tungstophosphate (NN-ZWP), it was found that Pb^{2+} is practically strongly sorbed on NN-ZWP at the considerable conditions only while copper and cadmium are sorbed only if they are weakly complexes at pH 6.5.

In the present paper, NN-ZWP is found to be quite suitable for making a Pb^{2+} -selective electrode. An electrode constructed using NN-ZWP as an electroactive material in a poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC) membrane matrix showed high selectivity and sensitivity for Pb^{2+} .

Results and discussion

The critical response characteristics of the electrode were assessed according to IUPAC recommendations⁹. Hence, during the preliminary experiments, the chelating inorganic ion exchange resin (NN-ZWP) using as an electroactive material the potentiometric response of the Pb^{2+} -selective membrane is shown in Fig. 1. As seen, the slope of the corresponding potential plot is much expected Nernstian slope. The emf values of the PVC matrix membrane at varying concentrations of lead ions indicate a rectilinear range from 5.0×10^{-6} to $1.0 \times 10^{-1} M$. The slope of the calibration was found to be 25.6 mV/decade. The limit of detection, is determined usually from the intersection of the two extrapolated segments of the calibration graph was found to be $4 \times 10^{-6} M$. It is interesting to note that the use of the membrane electrode based on α -nitroso- β -naphthol under buffered condition of pH 4.5–5.0, the results in a wider range and nearly Nernstian behaviour.

The average time required for the membrane electrode to reach within ± 1 mV for the final equilibrium value after successive immersion of a series of Pb^{2+} -solutions, each having a 10-fold difference in concentration was ~ 40 s for concentration $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ and potentials remain constant for more than 5 min, after which only a very slow divergence is recorded. It is worthwhile to note that the sensing behavior of the membrane remained unchanged when the potentials recorded either from low to high concentrations or *vice-versa*. The ion selective membrane prepared could be used for at least 90 days without any measurable divergence.

Fig. 1. Calibration curve of Pb^{2+} -selective (NN-ZWP)-PVC based membrane electrode at pH 4.5–5.0

The pH dependence of the potential response of the proposed electrode at $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ concentration in the pH range 1–13 was investigated. The results revealed that the potential response remains constant over the pH range 5–9. In highly alkaline media, the potential decreased sharply due to the interference of OH^- while at low pH values is attributed to the competition of H^+ ions.

The performance of the sensor was also investigated in partially non-aqueous medium using water-methanol and water-ethanol mixture (Table 1). The membrane works satisfactorily in partially non-aqueous medium up to a maximum 10% content of methanol and ethanol. In these mixtures the working concentration range and slope remain almost the same. However, above 10% non-aqueous contents, the slope decreased appreciably which indicates that the sensor has become less sensitive to Pb^{2+} ions.

The selectivity behaviour is obviously one of the most important characteristic of an ion-selective electrode that is relative electrode response for the primarily cation over the other cations present in solution, which is usually expressed in terms of potentiometric selectivity coefficient

(K_{AB}^{pot}). In this work, the interference of other ions i.e. foreign ions with the primary cations, has been estimated by fixed interference method¹⁰. The fixed interference method is based on the semi-empirical Nilolsky-Eisenman equation (1).

$$E_{ISE} = E^{\circ} \pm \frac{RT}{Z_A F} \ln \left(a_A + \sum K_{AB}^{pot} (a_B)^{Z_A/Z_B} \right) \quad (1)$$

It is quite well known that the above equation works well in modeling the non-specific response of a membrane when the ions under investigation have the same charge, i.e. $Z_A = Z_B$, but the same is not well suited for ions having different charges i.e. $Z_A \neq Z_B$. Coefficients are either deceptively large or small depending on whether the ion of higher charge is considered as primary or interfering species. The values of selectivity coefficient are given in Table 2. From the data it is observed that bivalent ions e.g. Ba^{2+} and Cd^{2+} interfere

Table 1. Effect of non-aqueous solvents on calibration curve of Pb^{2+} -selective (NN-ZWP)-PVC membrane electrode

Solvent	Composition (v/v) %	Slope (mV/decade concentration change)
Water	–	25.6
Methanol	2	25.6
Methanol	5	25.6
Methanol	10	25.1
Ethanol	2	25.6
Ethanol	5	25.6
Ethanol	10	24.7

Table 2. Selectivity coefficients (K_{ij}) values of Pb^{2+} selective (NN-ZWP)-PVC membrane electrode for different cations

Metal ion	Selectivity coefficients (K_{ij})
Ca^{2+}	8.33×10^{-2}
Mg^{2+}	8.33×10^{-2}
Sr^{2+}	1.32×10^{-2}
Ba^{2+}	5.00×10^{-1}
Co^{2+}	2.78×10^{-2}
Ni^{2+}	2.78×10^{-2}
Cu^{2+}	3.84×10^{-2}
Cd^{2+}	5.00×10^{-1}
Zn^{2+}	8.62×10^{-3}
Hg^{2+}	1.67×10^{-2}
Al^{3+}	1.08×10^{-2}
La^{3+}	2.06×10^{-3}

to some limited extent in the estimation of Pb^{2+} by this membrane electrode. While the other cations do not interfere during the estimation of lead and have low selectivity coefficient values.

Analytical applications of the proposed Pb^{2+} ion selective electrode were found to work well under the laboratory conditions. It was successfully applied to the determination of lead in a soil sample from the lead acid baths taken near from many Lead Electroplating Factories, situated in Ghaziabad District Industrial area. From the membrane sensor's calibration curve, the lead contents (16.3 and 13.5 ppm) in the sample was found to be in close agreement with that determined by atomic absorption spectrometry (17.0 and 13.9 ppm).

The proposed sensor was also used as an indicator electrode in titration of Pb^{2+} with ($1 \times 10^{-2} M$) EDTA, and the resulting titration curve is shown in Fig. 2. As seen the amount of Pb^{2+} ions in solution can be accurately determined with the electrode.

Fig. 2. EDTA titration curve for (NN-ZWP)-PVC based membrane electrode.

Experimental

All the reagents used for the preparation of membranes and metals salts (nitrates) were of analytical reagent grade (B.D.H., U.K.). α -Nitroso- β -naphthol (Thomas Baker, India), zirconium oxychloride (B.D.H., U.K.) sodium tungstate, ammonium sodium hydrogen orthophosphate and tetracycline hydrochloride (C.D.H., India) and high molecular weight poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC) (Fluka, Switzerland) were used without further treatment. Metal solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water and standardized by appropriate methods.

Preparation of membrane :

The electroactive material required for the preparation

of membrane ion selective electrode (MISE) was of chelating inorganic ion exchange resin. The exchanger, zirconium(IV) tungstophosphate (ZWP) were synthesized as reported earlier¹¹ by mixing solutions of 0.1 M zirconium oxychloride, 0.1 M sodium tungstate and 0.1 M ammonium sodium hydrogen orthophosphate at a mixing ratio 2 : 1 : 2 and at 1–2 pH and converted into H^+ form as usual manner. Finally the sorption of α -nitroso- β -naphthol on zirconium(IV) tungstophosphate was done according to the procedure previously described⁶.

The membrane was prepared by adding diluent tetrahydrofuran (6 ml) containing PVC (0.6 g) to an electroactive material (NN-ZWP) (0.2 g). The resulting solution was carefully cast on a glass slide plate and left for slow evaporation to obtain a thin membrane¹². Then an appropriate size of membrane was cut from the master membrane and was mounted at the lower end of the membrane holder with araldite.

Potential measurements :

The membrane was equilibrated with 0.1 M $Pb(NO_3)_2$ solution for 3–4 days and the potential generated across the membrane was measured by setting up the following electrochemical cell assembly

Internal reference electrode	Internal solution	Membrane	Test solutions	Internal reference electrode
	0.1 M Pb^{2+}			

Saturated calomel electrodes (SCE) were employed as reference electrodes and all potential measurements were made by using an Equiptronic-India Digital Potentiometer [EQ 602] at $25 \pm 1^\circ$. Before each set of measurements, electrodes were conditioned overnight in an appropriate buffer solution containing 0.1 M $Pb(NO_3)_2$ solution.

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Agarwal *et al.* : Lead(II) selective sensor based on heterogeneous membranes of chelating *etc.*

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